

SOCIOGAMERS: integrating Virtual Reality for teaching sociology

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Abstract. This study explores the role of Virtual Reality (VR) tools in enhancing higher education learning. A work in progress, it examines a small-scale intervention where master's students in Game-Based Learning create VR content to address first-year Sociology students' learning challenges at the University of Turin. Using a circular, interdisciplinary approach, the study maps learning needs, develops VR tools, and implements them with new student cohorts to improve engagement and comprehension.

Keywords: Virtual Reality, Game-Based Learning, Sociology.

1 Introduction

The interest in Virtual Reality (VR) technologies has grown in the last decade, particularly in the field of university education and learning [1]. On the one hand, the Covid-19 pandemic forced a rethinking of the educational relationship, while on the other, the evolution of VR headsets has offered new technological possibilities to institutions, with improved performance and more affordable prices [2]. Alongside these drivers, the rise of learner-centered pedagogical models [3] has expanded the reflection on educational practice and contributed to a rethinking of new technologies, which had previously been used mainly in the field of entertainment. Indeed, learning tasks in VR facilitate the construction of experiential knowledge [4]. Students become active subjects in their own learning, and the entire educational process can become more engaging, motivating, and personalized [5]. These features of VR learning constitute areas of proximity with gamification and Game-Based Learning (GBL), enabling their integrated use [6]. Together, they can form an innovative educational tool, capable of enriching traditional learning processes and enhancing their effectiveness, as well as responding in an original way to the emergence of new educational demands and representing an advancement towards the digitalization of education [6].

The "Sociogamers" project explores the combined use of Virtual Reality and Game-Based Learning within three courses at the University of Turin, through a student-centered perspective with an interdisciplinary and circular approach. The study, which is still under development, involves a small-scale intervention where students from the Educational Sciences program (Sociology of Education and Game-Based Learning) actively contribute to the construction of VR content to address the difficulties of first-

year Sociology students (Network Society). The project is structured in sequential phases and extends over a two-year period. It began in the fall semester of a.y. 2025/25 with the analysis of the educational needs of Network Society students. In the winter semester of a.y. 2024/25 students of Educational Sciences program are actively working on the development of digital resources. Implementation of Sociogames and data collection will start in the fall semester of a.y. 2025/26, with the new cohort of Network Society students.

The project's objective is to improve and enhance the learning process across all involved courses. In the bottom-up construction of educational resources, Educational Sciences students will have the opportunity to develop their design skills and strengthen interpersonal abilities. For Sociology students, the final recipients of the "sociogames", the use of immersive experiences aims to facilitate the understanding of complex or abstract concepts, already identified as problematic nodes in the preliminary needs analysis.

In this paper, after an overview of the potential benefits of VR learning and the possible applications of these tools in the still underexplored field of sociological subjects, we will focus on describing the "Sociogamers" project. It is a work in progress project therefore this short paper provides information on the planned methodologies and expected results but does not yet provide data, as implementation and data collection will take place in the fall semester of a.y. 2025/26.

2 Theoretical background

2.1 Benefits of Virtual Reality for learning

The "multisensory engagement" [7] offered by VR environments can significantly influence learning, with positive effects on knowledge acquisition [4]. Several studies confirming its effectiveness compared to traditional methods or less immersive media [8]. The advantage is particularly evident in comparison to lecture-based methods and textbooks [9], while it is present but less pronounced and more ambiguous when compared to other digital tools [10].

Learning in virtual reality environments proves effective for acquiring both declarative knowledge and procedural knowledge, especially in contexts involving active student participation [10]. Additionally, VR supports the acquisition of abstract knowledge that can benefit from the visualization capabilities of this technology, with some studies confirming the transferability of knowledge acquired in simulations to real-world contexts [7], thus facilitating the often challenging link between theoretical learning and its practical application.

However, knowledge acquisition in I-VR is not merely a matter of "transmitting content in 3D format". The medium itself, with its characteristics of interactivity and immersion, influences how the educational experience is lived and how information is processed. It affects the recipients of the message [11], stimulating affective and cognitive reactions that, either directly or indirectly, impact overall learning outcomes [4]. The sense of presence and agency offered by I-VR environments [12] can make the process more engaging, encouraging active student participation and mobilizing their attentional resources.

It has also been shown that I-VR experiences tend to elicit positive emotions in participants, which can influence learning by indirectly improving student outcomes [5]. Additionally, immersive virtual reality environments can protect the emotional well-being of more vulnerable students or those with low self-esteem, helping to reduce negative emotions [13]. Among the various factors that influence learning, motivation emerges as one of the most significant. It can stimulate curiosity and foster task concentration, supporting greater awareness in the learning process and deeper, more durable acquisitions [12].

2.2 Virtual reality and game-based learning for teaching sociology

Although many studies highlight the benefits of applying Virtual Reality as a teaching support tool, its use is primarily widespread in scientific and technological subjects and only marginally touches the field of social sciences [5]. However, sociology students could also benefit from the opportunities offered by this technology and, more generally, from interactive and participatory teaching tools such as those proposed by Game-Based Learning (GBL). The use of games in sociology education is not new and can support students in understanding both macro-level social phenomena and specific microsociological objects of inquiry. Simulation also encourages the development of key critical analysis and reflection skills for the sociological perspective [14, 15]. Through GBL, learning can become more engaging and stimulating, making traditionally difficult and boring subjects, like statistics, more attractive and accessible. This approach can promote the practical application of theoretical concepts, stimulating student interest and active participation [16].

Although less studied and adopted in the sociological field, Virtual Reality can offer additional tools to enhance learning, used either independently or in combination with GBL. The sense of embodiment experienced in VR can foster greater emotional involvement of students, helping to raise awareness on some important political and social issues, for example by developing their intercultural sensitivity and competence [17]. Furthermore, VR could be applied to the teaching of social research techniques, particularly in interviewing methods. Already experimented with in social work [18], it could also be used in sociology to support the development of practical skills related to conducting qualitative interviews. Students would have the opportunity to test their knowledge and skills in a safe space, where mistakes do not have real consequences and the activity is aimed at error overcoming.

Virtual Reality can also help students develop sociological imagination [19] and a critical perspective on society, as demonstrated by a study where students took a VR tour of a New York neighborhood and reflected—through a pre-recorded narrative voice—on the relationship between urban space and inhabitants [20]. These tools allow for the study of social dynamics from a privileged perspective and facilitate the adoption of diverse and alternative points of view, sometimes minority perspectives. The “Sociogamers” project therefore aims to explore a new field of application for Virtual Reality in sociology teaching, contributing to bridging the gap between the potential offered by this technology and its actual use in the field of social sciences.

3 Method

The “Sociogamers” project stems from the desire to activate a synergy between social, cultural, and technological innovation within two Bachelor Degree Programs at the University of Turin: “Social Innovation, Communication and New Technologies” and “Educational Sciences”. With a circular and interdisciplinary approach, three courses are involved: Network Society, an introductory sociology course in the ICT curriculum, and Sociology of Education and Game-Based Learning, two courses with a digital orientation within the Educational Sciences curriculum.

The project aims to address specific learning needs: students of Network Society face significant difficulties in understanding the basic concepts of sociology and research methods, while students of Educational Sciences require the strengthening of design and digital skills, as well as the development of collaborative and interpersonal abilities. Furthermore, the latter group shows entry-level deficiencies and irregular academic careers, highlighting the need to enhance teaching through targeted engagement strategies based on the use of digital technologies.

The project, launched in the 2024/2025 academic year and currently ongoing, involves several development phases articulated according to the Design Thinking methodology. The mapping of educational needs in the Network Society course, which took place in the fall semester of a.y. 2024/25, identified critical intervention areas in both theoretical and methodological knowledge (based on the final tests of the previous a.y. 2023/24); these form the basis for the development of Virtual Reality educational resources. Such contents, called “sociogames”, are created through a bottom-up and student-centered approach by Educational Sciences students using the CoSpaces platform, combining educational design models with game design. Specifically, students of Sociology of Education develop sociological concepts that are difficult for first-year Network Society students to understand, following educational design templates provided by the instructors, while students of Game-Based Learning transform these contents into virtual educational resources.

The implementation will take place during the fall semester of a.y. 2025/26 involving first-year Network Society students who will use the digital resources with MetaQuest and/or PicoVR headsets. The implementation of the Sociogames and the data collection will take place according to the experimental methodology: students will be divided into two groups, a treatment group (i.e. those experimenting the sociogames) and a control group (not experimenting), each group will undergo an assessment of the competencies acquired. Data on the competences acquired by the control and treatment group will be compared using statistical methods. Moreover, students will also evaluate the usability of the games and provide feedback for the future development of the project, with the aim of refining the Sociogames for the following edition. The high adaptability of the interactive and immersive content will enable customization according to different cognitive styles, in line with the Universal Design for Learning perspective. These resources can also be easily adapted for application in other educational contexts. The final phase of the first cycle involves dissemination, during which the Sociogames will be made available for other universities, partners of the EU-funded project HESPRI.

4 Expected results

In line with the evidence reported in the literature, an improvement in the acquisition, retention, and transfer of sociological knowledge is expected for Network Society students, along with the development of design and project skills for Educational Sciences students. In particular, Network Society students will be required to employ and adopt appropriate methodological skills in simulated research experiences and demonstrate their ability to apply sociological concepts to social phenomena through the simulated experience of real-life situations.

The proposal for engaging and interactive activities will also address other needs identified in the preliminary analysis, such as the development of soft skills for the labor market [16, 21]. Educational Sciences students will have the opportunity to work both individually and in groups, testing their communication and social-relational skills, and learning to convey knowledge and ideas effectively. Besides supporting student learning, this project sets the ambitious goal of promoting the regularity of their academic careers.

As already noted, interactive, enjoyable, and engaging teaching methods and techniques mobilize affective-cognitive factors that influence learning, either directly or indirectly. Subjects perceived as “boring” can become more attractive, while less motivated students with low self-esteem can discover new interests and gain confidence in their abilities, achieving results comparable to those of their peers [13]. The active involvement and direct participation of students can therefore translate into higher attention levels and a greater willingness to attend classes regularly [22].

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